

Human-carnivores conflict-a review

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SUMMARY

Human-livestock-carnivores struggle is a uniting factor in the complicated challenge of a shared environment. Human-wildlife interactions and conflicts have persisted for millions of years on our planet. The number of extinct species has expanded considerably in this century. In the wild, half of the world's population has become extinct. Extinction rates in protected regions are alarmingly high. The worldwide war between predators and people for space and food has wiped off the entire wild population. An ecosystem, on the other hand, may be controlled from both the top down and the bottom up. This study also demonstrates close contact between humans and fauna, which might be useful for new areas of human-carnivore research, such as one fitness component.

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INTRODUCTION

Species are vanishing at a rate 100 times faster than natural background rates, and sustained habitat loss will result in a far higher extinction rate, with up to half of the world's species being extinct (May et al., 1995; Pimm et al., 1995). Carnivores cause harm or death to domestic animals and fowl, as well as endangering or killing people. Human carnivore conflict is currently regarded a serious conservation and pastoral livelihood concern because too many predator animals have been killed as a result of an increasing conflict position with the original people (Dar et al., 2009). Herbivores are especially susceptible since they often live in tiny groups, and population size is one of the most popular predictors of extinction.

According to Pimm *et al.* (1988), the loss of inhabitants from various places is the most alarming (wood Roffe and Ginsberg, 1998) and mortal activity transforms natural landscapes into patchwork of civilization, grazing pastures, and urbanization. This isolates natural zones, which isolates populations, resulting in the extinction of species (Brown, 1971; Bolger et al., 1991). The behaviors of herbivores are a major source of contention with humans since they diminish mortal tolerance. In certain areas, large herbivores not only kill the beast but also risk the lives of humans who live nearby. The incidence of fatal wildlife encounters (HWC), particularly those involving big herbivores, has increased in recent years (Gittleman *et al.* 2001), posing a serious danger to the survival of many fragile species globally (Distefano, 2008).

Large herbivores are vital creatures for their ecosystems, and their extinction threatens the natural variety of the entire ecosystem (Treves and Karanth, 2003).

Wild animals not only destroy the animal but also endanger the lives of individuals who live nearby in some locations (Altaf, 2018; Azad *et al.*, 2018; Chughtai *et al.*, 2018; Safeer *et al.*, 2018; Younus *et al.*, 2018; Ijaz *et al.*, 2020; Mumtaz *et al.*, 2021). The incidence of fatal wildlife encounters, particularly involving big herbivores, has grown in recent years (Gittleman *et al.* 2001), posing a major danger to many vulnerable species worldwide (Distefano, 2008). Large herbivores are important ecosystem organisms, and their extinction threatens the ecosystem's natural variety (Treves and Karanth, 2003). Slight concentration has been need to the competitive interactions of sympatric large herbivores (Kruuk 1972; Karanth and Sunquist 2000). Regardless of the number of competing herbivore species with enormously huge geographic areas, intrigued predation has the potential to be a significant driver affecting the viscosity and distribution of herbivore species (Caro and Stoner 2003; Altaf, 2016). Snow leopards, wolves, lynx and brown bears are among the creatures with the least amount of research, with the bulk of data being spotty or anecdotal. These exposed herbivores are planted in inhospitable alpine regions of Central Asia, notably Pakistan's northern corridor.

COMMON LEOPARD

Leopard predation on livestock is an important conservation concern in locations with limited resources all over the world. Any efforts to prevent human and leopard clash and protect the species at stake must be based on a thorough understanding of conflict patterns. A household survey was carried out in and around the “Machiara National Park in Azad Jammu and Kashmir, Pakistan”, to assess livestock losses due to leopard predation. Between June 2007 and August 2008, leopards murdered 301 animals. The extent of the loss varied by month, with May having the biggest payment. Small-bodied scapegoats and lambs were more susceptible than large-bodied animals. Goats were butchered in far greater quantities than normal. Domestic animals were killed at a greater rate at night than during the day. Nighttime protection measures have a significant influence on depredation. Extreme attacks occurred in dense and areas distant from the forests. The elements most closely associated with beast depredation were the loss of natural prey, herding practices, guarding, especially at night, and repetitive usage of regions where bloodsuckers were known to be hunting laboriously. The initial community's sentiments toward leopards were predominantly unfavorable, and greater efforts should be made to increase support for carnivore conservation. Researchers advocate substantial one-of-a-kind community education as well as forward-thinking mortal-leopard conflict resolution, notably through campaigning for carnivore-friendly beast protection measures (Kabir *et al.*, 2014).

Carnivore-herbivore battle is a natural wonder, and carnivore species have a right to live on our planet, yet their extinction rates are frightening. Leopard. As a result of the exponential expansion in human population, much of the world's woods have been converted to arable land or home areas, threatening animals such as leopards. It is also a major cause of conflict between leopards and humans. The current research was conducted in 30 villages in Azad Jammu and Kashmir to analyse

the mortal-leopard conflict in terms of beast depredation, mortal antecedents, and public perception of the leopard. Leopards, i.e. goats, lambs, cows, buffalos, and funks, were all observed preying on the creatures. Nonetheless, grazing by creatures, mortal participation, and insufficient husbandry have all been established as major drivers of fatal leopard conflict. Conservation education, as well as leopard and canine guards and beast heads, may aid in the prevention of mortal-leopard conflict (Chattha et al., 2013).

Human-animal conflicts can result in retaliatory killing, putting some wildlife species at risk. Asiatic black bears destroy crops and cattle, and they also attack people. We investigated whether human-bear interactions encouraged bear poaching in China's Sichuan Province. We interviewed locals in 429 15-kilometer cells across the domain regarding bear circumstances, population trends, attitudes toward bears, mortal-bear conflicts, responses to bear harm, and bear coddling. Bears attacked humans, raided fields, and slaughtered cattle. 50% and 43% of townies, respectively, expressed unfavourable and neutral attitudes about bears; negative opinions were more prominent among people who had past bear experiences or lived in places where bear issues were more likely. Despite the fact that killing bears was illegal, inmates in 117 prisons indicated that bear coddling was popular in their areas. Killing bears, however, was not substantially connected with damage; in fact, killing was more prevalent in areas where bear battles were not lethal. Birders slaughtered a large number of bears in return for a lucrative passage. Tibetans were harmed by bears and had negative opinions toward them, but because of their religious beliefs, they got less coddling than Han or Yi people. According to our research, mortal-wildlife contacts shaped people's attitudes about bears, but strong profitable impulses, not stations, caused illegal payments. While lessening mortal-bear confrontations may help to foster more positive attitudes toward bears and the nature reserves that preserve them, it will not address the species' fundamental issue (Liu *et al.*, 2011).

Relationships between humans and American black bears (*Ursus americanus*) have evolved from public feeding and observation of scrap-affected animals to civic bear education juggernauts centered on eliminating food attractants. We utilized a tone-administered check to evaluate how wildlife authorities in the United States, Canada, and Mexico respond to mortal-bear conflict, and we contrasted how chevaliers and bears are presently handled. 48 agencies responded to the questionnaire, including information on bear numbers, complaints, types of connections, and agency reactions. Only 15 of the 75 organizations who evaluated displaced problem bears believed relocation was a beneficial technique. Regardless of the initial political and legal settings, all agencies must seek to develop techniques for tracking and evaluating the success of their actions. By covering conduct and outcomes, agencies may establish innovations and move ahead in an adaptable operational framework (Spencer et al., 2007).

Human-black bear conflict has been a long-standing concern in North America's wildlife management. Conflicts in metropolitan areas are linked to uninterrupted expansion and extension of deadly populations, as well as growing vacuity of man-made attractants (e.g., scrap, birdfeed). Responding to civic bear disputes may be a complicated process with widely disseminated viewpoints. This exercise highlights the significance of understanding the foundation for resident geste

and comprehensions in mortal-black bear battle circumstances. Residents of two Colorado towns with a high number of mortal-black bear interactions completed online and mail-in surveys assessing their opinions about municipal black bears and their preferences for operation behaviour. Fifty percent of those polled had positive stations, 15 had negative stations, and 35 had a combination of the two. Stations and situational rudiments assessed the efficacy of regularly used operation reactions to mortal - bear combat. Counterclaims in this inquiry include expecting public support for operation behaviour and conveying operation goals (Don Carlos et al., 2009).

BROWN BEAR

Brown bears are highly threatened across their range owing to poaching, habitat degradation, and fragmentation, according to Bunnell and Tait (1981), although their ecological needs remain unknown. Because bears reproduce at the slowest rate of any terrestrial animal, their reproductive rate has a significant impact on population viability. A comprehensive action plan is necessary for the long-term management of bears, according to Bellemain *et al.* (2007). To be efficient, an action arrangement must be founded on solid natural data, such as precise approximation of population, status, and links with other populations. Brown bear population approximations are hard to get for these rare and secretive creatures.

According to Servheen (1990), brown bears (*Ursus arctos*) are critically endangered in Southern Asia, where tiny, isolated populations persist in inaccessible and rugged mountainous areas. According to Schaller (1977), the Himalayan brown bear, a mainly isolated species. This bear has been wiped out in its historical distribution zone in Pakistan, and it currently only persists in tiny groups in northern mountainous areas with weak connectivity. “Deosai National Park” is the main fort of Pakistan's brown bear population. Demographic surveys in 1993 revealed that Deosai National Park had no more than 20 individuals, according to Nawaz (2007). According to Nawaz, (2007) brown bears in Pakistan are today dispersed throughout three major mountain ranges, perhaps in seven populations. All of them are tiny and volatile populations. The “Deosai National Park” has the largest and most likely only increasing population. According to Hilderbrand *et al.*, (1999) a favorable relationship between bear food and reproductive success has been demonstrated in a variety of studies. LeFranc *et al.* (1987); Craighead *et al.* (1995) studied the brown bear and discovered that the brown bear consumes food based on its original vacuity. According to Schwartz *et al.* 2003, the brown bear (*Ursus arctos*) is an opportunistic feral with a wide geographical spread.

SNOW LEOPARD

Snow leopards can be found in 12 Central Asian nations, according to McCarthy and Chaperon (2003): China has up to 60% of the snow leopard's possible habitat. Because of the remote and fragile terrain, as well as the rare cat's uncommunicative nature, most of its range has yet to be explored or has only been researched intermittently. Because most of the snow leopard's territory is along international borders, determining the species' current condition and distribution with confidence is challenging. Jackson *et al.* (2006) found that the presently known range of snow leopards is insufficiently counterplotted due to limited financing, a lack of competent

wildlife biologists, and sensitive logistics that oppressively impede inspections throughout the snow leopard's high, harsh terrain.

According to the IUCN Red Data Book, the Snow leopard (*Uncia uncia*) is an encyclopedically endangered species (IUCN, 2002). As a result of stalking, the snow leopard's security in Chitral Gol National Park deteriorated from weak to grave by 1974. Schneider (1976). The snow leopard has total legal protection in Pakistan. The Government of KP, Northern Areas, has designated the snow leopard as a protected animal under the third schedule of their separate Wildlife Acts (Ahmad, 1994).

Fox (1994) assessed the snow leopard range in Pakistan to be approximately km², whereas Schaller (1976) estimated the entire population to be between 100 and 250, and Hussain calculated it to be between 300 and 420. (2003). A 300-square-kilometer region in Chitral, which is known for its snow leopards, was combed, but only four or probably five were discovered (Schaller, 1976). There are no estimates of viscosity, but assuming a mean viscosity of 1/250 km², Pakistan's entire population would be roughly 320 snow leopards. Snow leopards may also be found in the Hindu Kush range in Chitral, as well as the Karakorum Range in Gilgit, Hunza, and Baltistan's northern areas. Although no viscosity estimate is known, the Shimshal region of Hunza boasts a big number of snow leopards (Wegge, 1988). Its existence in Azad Kashmir Province remains unclear (Roberts 1977).

Fox and Chundawat (1988) revealed that whereas snow leopards generally prey on Ibex, blue lamb, tahr, and other mountain beasts, when they go to the lower mound, they hunt on deer, wild boar, and hare. Chundawat and Rawat (1990) discovered that snow leopards ingested a substantial amount of manufacturing rubbish during their waste research. The waste study also indicated that one industrial species, *Myricaria germanica*, accounted for 65 percent of all factory debris and was discovered in 25 scats. The snow leopard ingested five blue lambs, twenty-five marmots, five domestic scapegoats, one domestic lamb, nine Tibetan woolly hair, and fifteen catcalls on a daily basis. They discovered that blue lamb, the most prevalent prey species, accounted for 50% of the biomass consumed by snow leopards.

Mukherjee *et al.* (1994) assessed the least number of hairs to analyse every waste and the minimum number of scats to estimate the leopard diet in Gir forest, India. He identified prey species using the same hair characteristics used in the current study. He was able to identify different prey species using only 20 hairs. Only 48% of the scats were planted with a single prey species, while the remainder was planted with a variety of prey species. Maheshwari and Sharma (2010) examined snow leopard eating patterns using waste analysis in a recent study done in India. Prey species were connected to the base of hair remains in the scats after examining their distinctive cuticle and medulla pattern under a microscope. Six different prey species were found in scats. The domestic beast (mule, scapegoat, and lamb) accounted for 36% of the snow leopard's diet, with blue lamb (18.2) and rodents accounting for the remainder (18.2). According to Hussain, (2003) snow leopards are limited to the Central Asian highlands, including major areas in the Altay, Lun, Pamir, Tien Shan, Kun, Himalaya ranges, Hindu Kush, and Karakoram.

LYNX

The lynx is one of 36 felid species present globally, according to Heptner and Sludskii (1972). The Eurasian Lynx is also found in China's Gansu, Shaanxi, Qinghai, and Sichuan provinces, as well as Uzbekistan, Turkmenistan, Kyrgyzstan, Pakistan, Mongolia, Kazakhstan, and Tajikistan, according to Roberts (1997). Din and Nawaz (2010) reported finding lynx in Pakistan's Chitral District and Gilgit Baltistan. They said that all prior reports were based on anecdotal evidence or expert opinion, with no attempt to document or disseminate information on a scientific foundation. As a result, the existing information is dubious. As a result, the purpose of this study was to collect the first-ever data on this fugitive species in Pakistan's District Chitral.

The preferred lynx niche, according to Parker *et al.* (1983), comprises of a diversity of timber topography and a mosaic of sequential phases that give a niche during both the idle and summer seasons. Quinn and Thompson (1987) studied the range of the lynx in relation to the availability of suitable timber. When compared to pure boreal timber, they estimate a boreal mixed wood timber has a relatively high Lynx carrying capacity. Boreal mixed wood forest damaged by logging or bumping is also regarded to provide a better lynx niche than genuine boreal woodlands.

Lynx require a diversity of leaf conditions to survive and reproduce effectively, both individually and in groups, according to Koehler and Aubry (1994). Rustling necessitates the use of wood species that can maintain large prey populations. Denning and mouser cover, like dead fields, require mature timbers or timbers with certain structural qualities. Open, grazed wood provides trip protection. Even if the final niche isn't necessary for lynx survival, trip cover can assist bridge the gap between the rustling and dining zones. Murray *et al.* (1994) found that lynx named areas of truly unconstrained sharp (> 76 covers) once, avoided open cover types twice, and avoided willow cover types once. Open enhance was the most popular cover type in all times (35-43% of the time) (26-50 cover).

According to Jobin *et al.* (2000), lynx typically feed on a kill for many days, caching throughout the day. If a sub-adult lynx stayed at the same position for two consecutive days, we were able to find it exactly by homing into a distance of 25-50 m the following night. The following day, this region was thoroughly examined, with a bloodhound occasionally used to locate a kill. The diet of the sub-grown-ups in the Natal disbandment of Eurasian lynx was compared to that of the resident lynx by Jobin *et al.* (2000).

According to Mowat *et al.* 2000, lynx primarily consume snowshoe hare, but at low points in the hare population cycle, alternate prey species are used. According to Apps (2000; Mowat *et al.* 2000, lynx, like white-tagged deer and mule deer, will scavenge on road-killed ungulates. According to Fuller (2004), small prey species eaten by lynx include red squirrel, northern flying squirrel, ruffed beef, marten and voles; while Lynx can kill deer in deep snow.

WOLF

The Indian wolf evolved during the Pleistocene's drier epoch to exploit a comparatively unfilled niche as top carnivores, according to Shahi (1982). Wolves are supposed to have developed as predators of massive ungulates in the boreal forest

environment; hence the Indian wolf's scarcity is surprising. The woodland is favored over scrubland grassland and semiarid pastoral/agriculture areas. Wolves, according to Ballard *et al.* (1983), are extremely successful dispersers, covering up to 732 kilometers in 9 months.

Gray wolves are well-known creatures belonging to the Canidae family of the Order Carnivora, according to Mech and Boitani (2003). The wolf, one of the most versatile mammals, may be found all across the planet, from Alaska to Saudi Arabia.

According to Roberts, 1997 two wolf subspecies are thought to exist in Pakistan. Two of them are Tibetan wolves and Indian grey wolves. The Tibetan wolf can be found in Chitral, Upper Swat, Baltistan, Gilgit, Khunjerab and Hunza in Pakistan's bleak alpine valleys. According to the IUCN, (2003) the grey wolf can be found in the deserts of Punjab and Baluchistan. Grey wolves can currently be found in "Khirthar National Park", "Chumbi Surla wildlife sanctuary", "Hazar Ghanji Chiltan National Park", "Hingol National Park", "Dureji game reserve", and "Lal Sohanra National Park".

According to Jhala, grey wolves are predators of ungulates in many dry and semi-arid settings (1993). Because of its small size, the grey wolf may survive on small animals like goats and lambs, as well as small prey like hare and rodents. Locusts, other insect reptiles, birds, and plant materials, such as *Prosopis chilensis* pods and *Ziziphus* spp., are also eaten by these wolves. Donkeys and camel calves have been preyed upon by grey wolves. According to Jhala (1993), wild ungulates make up the majority of a grey wolf's diet in the mountains. They also regularly murder domestic dogs, with a proclivity for cannibalism on the outskirts of mountain villages. Due to their predation on domestic goats and sheep, wolves are hunted in Pakistan, and their numbers are likely to continue to decline.

Claudia *et al.* (2004) compared the diet composition of resident packs in three research locations and analyzed the eating behaviors of wolf populations in varied ecological settings using scats. Wild gazelles were the most common food source, accounting for 89.4 percent to 95.1% of the diet. Livestock, on the other hand, seldom topped 8% of annual mean percent volume in any one location, and they were only significant in the Alps in the fall. Other food products accounted for just around 5% of the annual average volume. Although certain intra-specific selection tendencies were observed in each area, the quantities of wild ungulate categories utilised varied between the research sites.

According to Mech (1995), wolves' habitat flexibility means that they can live in any environment that supports their prey. Topographic features such as slope, height, and forest type, according to Alexander *et al.* (1996), impact prey availability, which may limit wolf mobility through terrain. Elevations over 1850m, slopes more than 30 degrees, and SSW aspects have all been found to be detrimental to wolf occurrence in the Central Canadian Rocky Mountains. The forest, according to Alexander *et al.*, offers wolves with dining and meeting places, as well as protection and concealment.

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